

AN ARCHIVAL STUDY OF LSB GALAXIES IN THE LOCAL UNIVERSE

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ABSTRACT

We present an archival study aimed at documenting, and finding statistical trends in **LSBs** (*low surface brightness galaxies*). LSBs are typically too faint to be studied in detail, due to their diffuse structure, and therefore remain poorly understood. Notwithstanding this, many LSBs contain key information regarding stellar evolution, star-forming regions, population II stars, and dark matter distribution. The goal of this paper is to identify statistical trends, derive photometric data, and develop analytical approximations about these galactic bodies. For this study, we selected a primary sample of **31** galaxies and a statistical sample of **212** galaxies. Many of these galaxies are formally classified as dwarfs but still meet the requirements for inclusion as LSBs. While no universally accepted definition exists, we adopt a working criterion of galaxies with measured surface brightness of **22 to 33 mag/arcsec⁻²**, **redshift 0.0001-0.2** for the **statistical example**, and **0.0001-0.09** for the **primary sample** (where redshift is defined as $z = \frac{\lambda_{obs} - \lambda_{rest}}{\lambda_{rest}}$ for low z systems) for systems beyond **$z=0.093$** we apply corrections for cosmological surface brightness dimming. The galaxy designated as our reference LSB is Malin 1, an ultra-faint spiral galaxy with an approximate absolute magnitude ≈ -22.9 (*Pickering, 1997-Malin 1: A Quiescent Disk Galaxy*)

INTRODUCTION

This observational study was conducted to identify statistical trends among low surface brightness (**LSB**) galaxies. These trends focus on the correlation between size and magnitude (mag/arcsec^{-2}), as well as the connections among luminosity, mass, and gravitational effects. The primary sample selected for this work consists of **31** galaxies spanning a redshift of $z=0.0001-0.09$. Data for each object are provided in the table on page (6), with additional information available in the associated dataset (<https://zenodo.org/records/18735788>).

LSB galaxies are notoriously difficult to study due to their unusually diffuse structures; however they can also be extremely massive. For example, **Malin 1**, a giant diffuse (*GLSB*) galaxy, is roughly six times larger than the **Milky way**. Many astronomers suggest, supported by simulation-based estimates, that LSB galaxies may be among the most numerous galaxies in the universe, although many are too diffuse to study in detail with current observational technology.

LSB galaxies are particularly important for understanding dark matter, as they are among the most dark matter dominated systems known. Some LSBs galaxies are estimated to consist of approximately **95%** dark matter, while the Milky way is thought to contain roughly **80-93%**. ([Clayton, Jeffery E.; McCloskey, Sue Ellen; and Braithwaite, Wilfred J. \(1996\) "Estimating Milky-Way Dark-Matter: Its Amount and Distribution," Journal of the Arkansas Academy of Science: Vol. 50, Article 23.](#)) Even this relatively small difference could produce massive significant gravitational effects via dark matter halos (*see N-body diagrams on page 7-11*) and may be a catalyst for minor galactic

groups. Their stellar populations are often diverse: some LSBs dwarfs are dominated by **young, metal rich stellar populations** and star-burst regions. While larger, more diffuse LSB galaxies tend to consist of **mature, population II stellar populations** (*population II stars originated 100m-600m years after the big bang, being metal-poor and extremely efficient*).

METHODS + FINDINGS

In selecting sample LSBs, we aimed to include a diverse set of galaxies to estimate a representative median and to map the available data. To achieve this we selected at random 31 discovered, and undocumented LSB galaxies. We employed Python scripts to query various databases and surveys ([SIMBAD](#), [VIZIER](#), [NED](#)), establishing a pipeline to exclude galaxies exceeding a specified surface brightness threshold of μ **22 to 33 mag/arcsec⁻²**. When analyzing our primary sample of **31 LSB** galaxies we found several intriguing results. Many of these LSBs tend to fall into a range of 'LSB dwarfs' which are not fully classified as LSBs based on their apparent brightness, and brightness per *mag/arcsec⁻²*. Some galaxies were identified as potential AGN candidates based on anomalous photometric band measurements, even if their overall surface brightness per *mag/arcsec⁻²* showed them to be incredibly diffuse. Any such anomalies were removed due to the possibilities of inaccurate data. Below is information on **Z 42-137** which we have found to fit into the 'LSB dwarf range' ; while its absolute magnitude ($M \approx -14.45$) is faint, it is still brighter than several objects in the primary sample group.

Z 42-137 LSB DWARF TABLE (SELF DERIVED + SIMBAD DATA)

Table one: Z 42-137

ID	Redshift	μ mag/arcsec ⁻²	LxW arcminutes	z	i	g
Z 42-137	0.005472 S	$\mu \approx 25.05$	0.8297 0.5101	–	19.8	15.8

Using the Cosmological comoving distance formula, $d_C(z) = d_H \int_0^z \frac{dz}{E(z)}$ where $d_H = c/H_0$ $c = 2.998 \times 10^5$ km/s (where $H_0 = 70$) and $E = \sqrt{\Omega_r(1+z)^4 + \Omega_m(1+z)^3 + \Omega_k(1+z)^2 + \Omega_\Lambda}$. We get a comoving distance of roughly **23.14 Mpc**. Using this we can find the angular size of the galaxy where $D(kpc) = d_{(Mpc)} a_{(arcmin)}$ (0.2902), which shows **Z 42-137** has a **diameter** of roughly **5.56 kpc**, with an absolute magnitude of ≈ -14.45 . The data was aggregated by averaging the reflectance values across all listed bands then using, $M = 17.37 - 5 \log_{10}(\frac{d}{10pc})$ (where $d = 23.14$) = **-14.45** (Surface brightness of roughly **25.5 mag/arcsec⁻²**), all magnitudes used were derived from SED fluxes across photometric bands. Following the extraction of physical parameters from our primary sample of 31 LSB galaxies, we performed comparative analysis via diagnostic plotting to identify shared scaling relations (Via Python codes to computer data plots, find statistical trends, and filter false positives).

GRAPH ONE: PRIMARY SAMPLE GROUP (Bootstrap ran 1000x)

This first graph shows us the relationship between Absolute magnitude, Galaxy size (Kpc), and Mean surface brightness (mag/arcsec⁻²). Analyzing this work we can see a trend among the two sub categories of LSB galaxies. The dwarf LSB galaxies

form the most common class of LSBs and comprise nearly 60% of our sample (*This was likely attributable to a detection threshold of approximately magnitude 30 for most major surveys*). Over time, these dwarfs often accumulate near larger galaxies, evolving into satellite systems. The largest and most diffuse outliers, such as Malin 1 and LEDA 42527, represent the absolute extremes, exceeding 200 kpc in diameter while remaining extremely diffuse. These massive, diffuse outliers require isolated, 'void-like' regions of space to persist; ([Bustos-Espinoza, R. O. E., Blaña, M., Galaz, G., Mora, M., Junais, M., Das, M., Barway, S., Kumar, A., Johnston, E. I., & Puzia, T. \(2025\). Exploring the stellar streams and satellites around the giant low surface brightness galaxy Malin 1 \(arXiv:2502.11041\)](#) otherwise, their outer halos or spiral structures are easily perturbed by nearby galaxies (*LEDA 42527—which has three cosmological neighbors within a projected radius of 3 arcminutes: derived via Python scripts*). The majority of the samples exhibit a trend of increasing surface brightness as size decreases, while a secondary trend shows a gradual 'plateau' in brightness as object size increases. We estimate the mean absolute magnitude to be approximately -15.7. (*using median measurements across bands*)

Primary sample table 1-31 (all photometric bands $\pm 0.15\sigma$ to account for rounding and measurement error)

Table two. This table presents all derived quantities for the primary sample, with parameters calculated from and compiled using the referenced observational datasets, [SimBad.cds](#), [Ned.ipac](#), [SDSS.org](#) (all epochs). All data has been filtered and passed Python pipeline scripts. (NULLS + COORDIANTES IN DATASET)

ID	Redshift _(S-SPECTROSCOPIC OR EMISSION)	μ mag/arcsec ⁻²	LxW arcminutes	z	i	g
EGCC-1.195	0.065±0.0195	$\mu \approx 23.6$	0.117 0.093332	–	–	–
LEDA 42758	0.0038	$\mu \approx 22.7$	0.295623 0.283946	17.1	15.7	16.7
SMDG J	0.05±0.02	$\mu \approx 24.31$	0.193 0.193	19.2	–	19.2
LEDA 41922	0.003382±0.000446	$\mu \approx 22.6$	0.202243 0.19207	17.8	16.6	17.5
LEDA 41993	0.00444 S	$\mu \approx 22.22$	0.14648 0.129503	18.7	16.8	17.7
SMDG J	0.02±0.015	$\mu \approx 25.62$	0.26301 0.26301	20.6	21.4	18.7
EGCC-1.357	0.03±0.025	$\mu \approx 24.83$	0.2418 0.35002	18.5	18.8	18.7
SMDG J	0.079±0.0293	$\mu \approx 25.62$	0.4456667 0.4456667	15.7	17	18.1
LEDA 4010979	0.019844±0.00001	$\mu \approx 23.39$	0.251417 0.211366	17.6	17	18.3
LEDA 42792	0.003261±0.001	$\mu \approx 26.25$	0.4 0.4	19.3	18.9	19.7
LEDA 42527	0.07701±0.00013	$\mu \approx 29.81$	1.27 1.27	19.3	21	21.8
[PDK2018] VLSB25	0.04±0.0208	$\mu \approx 26.49$	0.4393 0.4393	–	19	20
LEDA 42320	0.07±0.055	$\mu \approx 22.59$	0.20374 0.102277	18.8	17	19.8
[GKP2005] 107	0.04±0.03607	$\mu \approx 23.68$	0.117334 0.117334	20.3	20.1	18.6
[GGS2018] 52	0.031±0.03002	$\mu \approx 23.97$	0.2507 0.2507	–	18.2	18.8
EGCC-1.352	0.04±0.02	$\mu \approx 27.60$	0.1209 0.1209	22.8	23.8	23
LEDA 1109735	0.01±0.0085	$\mu \approx 23.09$	0.314867 0.210772	16.9	–	18
COMA 22 8013	0.03±0.01	$\mu \approx 24.19$	0.059 0.0621	–	–	–
COMA 22 7843	0.035±0.015	$\mu \approx 24.85$	0.093713 0.0759075	–	–	22
LEDA 1088771	0.021±0.004	$\mu \approx 23.14$	0.194507 0.101649	18.8	17.8	19.5
MALIN 1	0.082702 S	$\mu \approx 24.70$	2.1 2.5	15.8	–	18.4
LEDA 39621	0.007873 S	$\mu \approx 28.57$	0.3162 0.212794	–	22.9	–
Z 42-137	0.005472 S	$\mu \approx 25.05$	0.8297 0.5101	–	19.8	15.8
SDSS J	0.00167 S	$\mu \approx 24.55$	0.663 0.663	16.3	16.3	16.7
MCG+03-32-011	0.004299 S	$\mu \approx 23.92$	0.38642 0.326138	16.9	18.6	17.4
LEDA 39942	0.006224 S	$\mu \approx 28.24$	1.33 0.67	20	20.4	17.1
LEDA 40083	0.00306 S	$\mu \approx 23.46$	0.30179 0.206153	17.5	16.5	18.6
LEDA 40159	0.055±0.0102	$\mu \approx 22.80$	0.0584867 0.0411337	21.4	18.3	22.1
LEDA 41219	0.039±0.025	$\mu \approx 28.32$	0.1828 0.1828	20.3	20.8	–
LEDA 41311	0.007302±0.0021	$\mu \approx 26.81$	0.89 0.51	–	–	15.9
LEDA 41428	0.00352±0.00133	$\mu \approx 22.96$	1.556667 1.556667	15.5	14.5	16.5

(All surface brightness values mag arcsec^{-2} are calculated using the median of all available and/or derived bands, not just those explicitly listed. Missing photometric values unavailable in query attempts)

Citations: ([Alexei Y. Kniazev](#),[Eva K. Grebel](#),[Simon A. Pustilnik](#),[Alexander G. Pramskij](#),[Tamara F. Kniazeva](#),[Francisco Prada](#),[Daniel Harbeckar](#)[Xiv:astro-ph/0310644\(2003\)](#), [SimBad](#), [VizieR.SED](#))

Primary sample N-body diagrams n3 (all diagrams were derived on Python, Nulls in dataset)

GRAPH TWO: sample group N-Body diagram (estimated density models-generated via Python *matplotlib*), the first three galaxies contain a simulation of its morphology, stellar mass density regions, and estimated dark matter (DM) halo (estimating based on median due to unreliable data 96% of objects mass is dark matter). Simulation one, Stellar density. Simulation two Dark matter halo ($\approx 96\%$ DM) ([de Blok et al. 1997](#))<https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/290.3.533>)

Effective Radius (kpc): 11.749443395076522

Virial Radius (kpc): $\approx 71.54329033353645$

Absolute Magnitude: -17.61556232620698

Stellar Mass (M_{sun}): $\approx 1611591344.216484$

Dark Matter Mass (M_{sun}): $\approx 38678192261.19558$

DMmass % 96

Effective Radius (kpc): 115.32833275841371
 Virial Radius (kpc): ≈ 345.984998275241
 Absolute Magnitude: -17.019228234964032
 Stellar Mass (Msun): $\approx 930510524.6834638$
 Final Dark Matter Mass (Msun): $\approx 4374528433076.699$
 DMmass % 96

Effective Radius (kpc): 221.963077045385
 Virial Radius (kpc) $\approx 370.07320512417436$
 Absolute Magnitude: -20.424130896094496
 Stellar Mass (Msun): $\approx 42826476991.83086$
 Dark Matter Mass (Msun): $\approx 5353309623978.856$
 DMmass % 96

These findings match observations derived by—[\(Bustos-Espinoza, R. O. E., Blaña, M., Galaz, G., Mora, M., Junais, M., Das, M., Barway, S., Kumar, A., Johnston, E. J., & Puzia, T. \(2025\). Exploring the stellar streams and satellites around the giant low surface brightness galaxy Malin 1 \(arXiv:2502.11041\).\)](#)

96% chosen from literature estimates of 90-99% (Gregory Bothun, 1998, <https://ned.ipac.caltech.edu>, de Blok et al. 1997 <https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/290.3.533>)

(All estimates shown were derived via python script, SED flux to mag calculations, and cosmological equations used include $M_{\text{halo}}=f(M^*)$, $(3M_{\text{halo}}/4\pi\Delta\rho_{\text{crit}})^{1/3}$, $DM\approx 96\%M$) Planck $H_0=67.4$, $\Omega_m=0.315$, $\Omega_b=0.046$, $\Omega_\Lambda=0.685$, $\Omega_\Lambda=0.685$, Stellar mass $M^*=L\times M/L$, luminosity $L=10^{-0.4(M_{\text{abs}}-M_{\text{abs}}^\odot)}$, Flux to magnitude $m_{\text{ab}}=-2.5\log_{10}\left(\frac{F}{3631}\right)$

GRAPH THREE: STATISTICAL SAMPLE

The statistical group was derived in Python via Astroquery, and VizieR surveys which were then cross matched with SDSS data for accurate redshift and photometric measurements. (all error bars factored in)

The figure shown was generated using Python scripts executed over a continuous three-hour period. It displays the original sample group (red stars— see Page 5) alongside the derived statistical sample of 212 galaxies (black dots). All galaxies included satisfy the

selection criteria described below, chosen to exclude outliers and non-LSB systems: μ 22 to 33 mag/arcsec⁻², 0.2 arc min diameter minimum, redshift 0.0001-0.2 (all galaxies beyond $z=0.093$ corrected for cosmological surface dimming). About 98.3% of all sampled galactic bodies reside below 25Kpc, while outliers such as **Malin 1** (200-220 Kpc) remain significantly separated from the

primary distribution, consistent with outlier behavior. The median surface brightness was measured to be $\mu = 23.6 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$ (accounting for statistical sample and primary sample).

DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

Our statistical example indicates that the LSB galaxy's population is dominated by compact dwarf systems containing low stellar mass and older, mature stellar populations ([James Schombert, Stacy McGaugh, Case Western Reserve U. Tamela Maciel, Cambridge U. 2013](#)) Jun 18, 2013. These dwarf LSBs exhibit high inferred dark matter fractions (<https://ned.ipac.caltech.edu> [Gregory Bothun, 1998](#)). Only a small percentage of these LSB systems occupy the extremes regime of ultra diffuse spirals ([Steven R. Janssens et al 2019 ApJ 887 92](#)). We observed a gradual increase in surface brightness with decreasing effective radius, suggesting a structural transition between LSB dwarf systems and larger, more diffuse systems. This behavior is broadly consistent with previous studies of LSB scalings (<https://ned.ipac.caltech.edu> [Gregory Bothun, 1998](#)), which reports similar trends in disk surface density. However, our derived mean absolute magnitude of ($M \approx -15.7$), and mean (mag/arcsec^{-2}) of $\mu 23.6$ is slightly fainter than (1998), ([Isha Pahwa, Kanak Saha, Structural properties of faint low-surface-brightness galaxies, Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society, Volume 478, Issue 4, August 2018, Pages 4657–4668, https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty1139](#)) which reported a median of (μ_0 being 21 and 22.5 mag arc sec⁻²), likely reflecting our stricter surface

brightness selection criteria. The dark matter fraction ($\approx 96\%$) falls within range commonly reported for LSB galaxies (*de Blok et al. 1997* <https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/290.3.533>), Reinforcing the interpretation that these LSB systems are among some of the most dark matter dominated disk galaxies known. Within Λ CMD frameworks, such dominance is commonly associated with halos of elevated spin parameters, in which baryonic collapse remains inefficient. (*1986, 10.1086/163867, Blumenthal, G. R. ; Faber, S. M. ; Flores, R. ; Primack, J. R.*) These structural properties observed match compatibility with these interpretations. Observations of the extreme systems, such as Malin 1, and LEDA 42527 show they occupy a parameter space well separated from the bulk sample, with diameters exceeding 130Kpc. Other studies derived these GLSBs to have quiescent, massive disks embedded in an extended halo (*Bustos-Espinoza, R. O. E., Blaña, M., Galaz, G., Mora, M., Junais, M., Das, M., Barway, S., Kumar, A., Johnston, E. J., & Puzia, T. (2025). Exploring the stellar streams and satellites around the giant low surface brightness galaxy Malin 1 (arXiv:2502.11041). arXiv. https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.11041*). Our derived halo parameters are broadly consistent with these observations. Though, our slight discrepancy in halo mass and size ($\pm 10^5 M_{\odot}$, $\pm 40\text{Kpc}$) likely reflect differences in assumed virial overdensity and cosmological parameters. Our halo mass estimates assume virial equilibrium and simplified mass to light ratios, which may introduce systematic uncertainties and error bars. Future spectroscopic and kinematic measurements would be required to refine our estimates. The dominance of dwarf systems within our sample likely reflects limitations of current observational data and detection limits of surveys

such as SDSS. Predetermined Python pipeline parameters likely rejected certain groups deemed too bright or diffuse to properly measure, also limiting the number of larger galactic bodies. Our future work hopes to tighten estimates derived and calculate dark matter halos for a larger number of LSB systems. We hope to begin a project mapping IFN in the Orion Cygnus arm. This project aims to systematically map IFN to a limiting depth of 28th magnitude, while simultaneously establishing a long-term, citizen-driven observational program designed to push our understanding of the faint structure and extended components of the Galaxy to unprecedented limits. Our plan for this project is to begin work around early April, and continue into 2028. We also hope to expand the EGC catalog ([Ehrlund, E. \(2026\). EGC Ehrlund Galactic catalog in depth \[Data set\]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18578841>](#)) to host more objects long term and assist in other archival studies.

CITATIONS

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